

DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT STUDY SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM OF FUTURE COMPUTER SCIENTISTS

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Abstract. In this thesis, the essence of the credit-module system, which is characterized as a measure of the quality of education and is widely used in the implementation of educational programs, foreign experience of the problem, and the issues of creating a single standard of education are considered. The article also provides recommendations on improving the use of the credit-module system in education.

Keywords: Foreign experience, English, credit-module system, method, competence.

INTRODUCTION

When talking about the self-development of the future informatics in the credit-module system, the existing approaches to the problems of self-development in the philosophical-pedagogical and psychological imagination, focusing on the interdependence of self-development and cognitive activities, to distinguish the factors of self-development of the student personality. It is necessary to consider it in an aspirational way.

MAIN PART

Fundamental reforms in the world education system promote the problems of creating the necessary conditions for students to learn foreign languages perfectly, to be able to express themselves in all fields knowing a foreign language, and to develop their oral and written speech in a foreign language. Organizations such as UNESCO, UNICEF, Association of European Universities, European Network for Quality Assurance of Higher Education deal with the issues of students' ability to think in a foreign language, develop their intellectual activity, and evaluate their readiness. The development of this issue in general trends is of great importance in the formation of modernity and foreign language skills in the young generation, and serves to increase the creative abilities of students in connection with the problems of modern education. In reforming the education system of our republic, coordination with educational programs that conform to international standards based on foreign experiences became the basis for improving the higher pedagogical education system.

Currently, in the implementation of educational programs, the world practice uses the so-called credit-module systems, in which the credit is described as a measure of the quality of education. The concept of credit in this case means a quantitative feature that allows to take into account the contribution of each academic subject to the content of education and professional training. In relation to higher education, the term "module" refers to a documented logical unit of the educational and professional program of a subject.

Skilled, experienced teachers can put themselves in the place of the student and organize lessons accordingly. Therefore, he clearly and consistently plans the quality of the presentation and the mechanism of the lesson. It is well known that teachers of this type perform their activities in accordance with the requirements of the times. It is difficult to imagine the modern education system without the terms "competency" and "interactive method".

English is the most popular language in the world, it is spoken in more than 67 countries and is one of the six languages of the UN. No other language can boast such statistics. English is an international language, so in addition to general mental development, you will have many opportunities for travel, work, recreation and more. This method of teaching is slowly entering our education system.

Today, this system is used in many countries of the world to ensure the integration of all higher education institutions, to create a uniform standard of education, to establish academic mobility, and to unify professional competence.

The use of the credit system in European universities is included in many new laws on higher education (Poland, Greece, Sweden, Finland, Austria, Portugal, Norway, Ireland, Denmark).

For example, in Denmark, since 2001, it is mandatory, and according to it, the amount of educational units is shown in credits [1].

Based on this system, the educational process is primarily created as a tool, allowing to choose the general measure of education received by the student, necessary for his academic mobility. The need to create and develop a credit system as a mechanism for converting loans received by students is [2]:

- this system guarantees academic recognition of studying abroad;
- provides access to comprehensive training courses;
- ensuring the transparency of curricula
- may choose not to return to his home country after studying abroad;
- the possibility to stay at the host university to receive qualifications;
- continuous education process.

Credit-module system as units of measurement of student load, modular educational technologies and European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System

- ECTS is a model for organizing the educational process based on the unit of credits. The credit-module system of organizing the educational process is designed to positively solve the following conceptual tasks:

- dividing the subject material into modules, checking the mastery of each module;
- use of a wider scale of knowledge assessment; - increasing the transparency of education;
- encouraging systematic independent work of students during the semester; - increasing the share of independent education in the educational process;
- the ability to change educational programs based on the demand for specialists in the labor market;
- introduction of healthy creative and scientific competition in education.

CONCLUSION

Among the problems related to the field, insufficient didactic provision of the modern information-educational environment for increasing the practical competence of future informaticists, insufficient reflection of the definition of competence in educational programs; increasing critical and creative thinking of students, working with large amounts of data, and using design methods shows insufficient organization.

Suggestions and recommendations:

- effective use of design technologies in vocational training activities to increase practical competence;
- conducting pedagogical practice on the basis of educational institutions;

- development of cooperation technologies of teacher and student, which is the most important factor of the credit-module system.

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